

Comparative Study of Some Mechanical Properties of Hybrid Polymeric Composites Prepared by using Friction Stir Processing

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Abstract- In this study, it was investigated the effect of adding (graphite, Alumina (Al_2O_3) and Copper (Cu)) micro particles with different volumetric fractions (0, 2, 4 and 6%) as reinforcement materials into the binary polymeric blend consist of (85% high density polyethylene (HDPE):15% polyvinyl chloride (PVC)) as a matrix material to produce hybrid composite of polymeric materials through friction stir processing (FSP) technique. The results of mechanical tests showed that as the reinforcement powders were introduced to the matrix material, led to enhancements in each of the flexural strength, flexural modulus, and maximum shear stress. where it was increased by (38, 43 and 48 %) respectively. While impact strength and fracture toughness decrease by the ratio (6 and 20%) respectively. So, in this work, the volumetric fractions of powders added to the polymer surface was determined by using Response Surface Methodology (RSM). As well as, the results of the prepared samples, it was confirmed by Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometers (FTIR) test and Morphology test.

Keywords: polymer blends, hybrid composite materials, friction stir processing (FSP), mechanical properties.

1. Introduction

The main advantages of composite materials are their high strength and stiffness, combined with low density, when compared with bulk materials, allowing for a weight reduction in the finished part. The reinforcing phase provides the strength and stiffness. In most cases, the reinforcement is harder, stronger, and stiffer than the matrix [1]. The main factors that determine the mechanical and physical properties are type of metallic filler, distribution and volume fraction of particles, and the nature of the techniques used for producing composite materials. So, several techniques have been developed in the experimental investigation for producing of composite materials. In general, these methods utilize a combination of mixture temperature and method of mixing, such as mechanical milling, vacuum arc deposition, melt mixing and injection molding [2-5]. In the last years, considerable care has been spent to a novel composite fabrication technique called friction stir processing (FSP) [6 and 7]. Which is considered an innovative manner for the invention of composites, nanocomposites and microstructural adjustments [8]. (FSP) has found to be a suitable instrument for enhancing the mechanical properties of materials [9 and 10]. The FSP was received on the essential sources of friction stir welding (FSW) which was discovered at the UK Welding Institute (TWI) by Wayne Thomas in 1991, where this method is considered a method of solid-state welding [3]. Ehsan Azarsa & Amir Mostafapour demonstrated the possibility of improving some of the mechanical properties by synthesizing a composite material consisting of polymer-copper powder with a particle size $<45\mu m$ on the surface or bulk composite material by the (FSP) technique [11]. In the present work, studying the possibility of improving mechanical properties for polymeric surfaces by adding hybrid micro-powders (graphite, Al_2O_3 , and Cu) to binary polymer blend by using Friction Stir Processing Technique.

2. Experimental Approach

The material selected in the present study was a binary polymer blend (85%HDPE:15%PVC) as a matrix material, prefabricated as a plate of 8mm thickness and reinforcement materials which is hybrid micro-particles consist of (graphite, aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) and copper powder) were added at a volumetric fraction (0, 2, 4 and 6%) to produce hybrid polymeric composites. The average particles diameter of (Cu), (Al_2O_3) and (Graphite) were (45, 25 and 25 μm) respectively.

1. Milling Machine: Due to the lack of a specialized machine for the friction stir processing operation, the vertical milling machine was used for the purpose of working the hybrid polymeric composite materials. The

machine (model Knuth) made in China with various rotational speeds and transversal speed. In this work the rotational speed selected was (492) rpm and transversal speed was (24) mm/min.

2. Accessories of Equipment: Because of the vertical milling machine not designed for the friction stir process, therefore some special accessories were equipped, which help to fix the workpiece well and prevent them from moving and slide due to the force generated during the (FSP). Figure (1) illustrates these manufactured equipment's, were a flat backing plate with dimensions (400 mm x 300 mm x 20 mm) and two special strips (20 mm) thickness and (450 mm x 50 mm) cross section area, each strip clamped down on the machine bed by two bolts gauge (M 14). Both of backing plate and two strips are made of medium carbon steel.

Figure 1. Clarification of manufactured equipment accessories.

3. Friction Stir Processing Tool: For the purpose of taking advantage of the greatest proportion of heat generated from the shoulder and because there is great contact between tool and matrix material, the design of the tool has been changed considering both the pin and the shoulder Penetrates the workpiece plus changing the shape of the pin as shown in Figure (2) in order to increase the surface area of the pin and thus increase the amount of heat generated and consider the part that looks like the shoe just a base preventing the volatilization of molten polymer materials as well as the reinforcement particles.

Figure 2. sketch of shoe tool.

4. Experimental Step: In the current work, samples of polymeric hybrid composites were prepared which consist of binary polymer blend, (85%HDPE:15%PVC), as a matrix material and reinforced with different volumetric fractions of the following micro-particles ((C), (Al₂O₃) and (Cu)) which were added as hybrid mixture. The central composite design CCD was used to perform the experiments, having eight as a corner point, six as axial points and six as central points, so, the totality of experimental number is 20 experiments as shown in (Table.1).

Table 1. Coded and actual values of the variables.

Test No.	C %		Al ₂ O ₃ %		Cu %	
	Coded	Actual	Coded	Actual	Coded	Actual
1	0	4	0	4	0	4
2	0	4	0	4	1	6
3	-1	2	0	4	0	4
4	0	4	0	4	0	4
5	0	4	1	6	0	4

6	1	6	0	4	0	4
7	0	4	0	4	-1	2
8	0	4	-1	2	0	4
9	1	6	1	6	-1	2
10	-1	2	1	6	1	6
11	1	6	-1	2	1	6
12	0	4	0	4	0	4
13	0	4	0	4	0	4
14	-1	2	-1	2	-1	2
15	0	4	0	4	0	4
16	-1	2	-1	2	1	6
17	1	6	1	6	1	6
18	-1	2	1	6	-1	2
19	1	6	-1	2	-1	2
20	0	4	0	4	0	4

For the purpose of configuring the (FSP) a special slot with different depths as illustrated in Table (2) was processed in the middle of selected binary polymer blend sheet, each one has the same surface area (8 mm width, 150 mm Length) the process was performed by a vertical milling machine. slices were cut off from (PVC) sheet with dimensions (1.01 mm) thickness and cross-section area (150 x 8 mm²), the three powders used in the current study, which are weighed by a sensitive balance mix well according to the specified percentages and then placed in the slot and covered with the (PVC) slice previously cut off, then mounted the sheet on the vertical milling machine for the purpose of conducting (FSP). All ratios for the twenty test represented in Table (2), which represent percentages of (graphite, Al₂O₃, Cu) powder are obtained from the design of experiment according to Response Surface Methodology (RSM)- Minitab 17 program.

Table 2. Reinforcement filler weights.

Test No.	Slot Depth (mm)	Slices Thickness(mm)	Reinforcement Weight (g)		
			Graphite	Al ₂ O ₃	Cu
1	1.334	1.01	0.264	0.474	1.068
2	1.338	1.01	0.226	0.406	2.060
3	1.302	1.01	0.079	0.569	1.282
4	1.334	1.01	0.264	0.474	1.068
5	1.403	1.01	0.226	0.914	0.915
6	1.403	1.01	0.509	0.406	0.915
7	1.302	1.01	0.317	0.569	0.320
8	1.270	1.01	0.317	0.142	1.281
9	1.400	1.01	0.509	0.914	0.229
10	1.400	1.01	0.057	0.914	2.060
11	1.400	1.01	0.509	0.102	2.060
12	1.334	1.01	0.264	0.474	1.068
13	1.334	1.01	0.264	0.474	1.068
14	1.150	1.01	0.132	0.237	0.534
15	1.334	1.01	0.264	0.474	1.068
16	1.323	1.01	0.080	0.142	2.884
17	1.437	1.01	0.396	0.711	1.602
18	1.324	1.01	0.079	1.280	0.320
19	1.333	1.01	0.713	0.142	0.320
20	1.334	1.01	0.264	0.474	1.068

After attended binary polymer blend sheet surface, the tool probe plunged slowly until aluminum base touched the matrix surface, the tool rotates at (492 rpm) clockwise, shoulder plunging depth is (0.5 mm) and dwell time is (30 second) which helps to soften the surface before starting the linear movement of the tool in order to get a flawless surface. Then (FSP) conducted on the surface of the sheet by an applied force from the tool which

moves at (24 mm/min) traverse speed. Plunging depth of the tool shoulder adjusted by monitoring the (FSP) face appearance (defect free or not) at the beginning of the process line. At the end of the (FSP) line, the linear and rotational speed of the tool is stopped and then lowering machine bed to retract the tool, this step leaves a hole at the end of the line which can be cut from the sheet as shown in the Figure (3). The samples are then cut according to the dimensions of each test.

Figure 3. shows (FSP) line.

3. Mechanical Testing

Flexural strength, flexural modulus and maximum shear stress were obtained through a three-point bending test, by using a universal testing machine (model WDW 200 E) made in China, the test was carried out at a crosshead speed of 5mm/min, all tests were carried out at a room temperature (23 ± 2 °C) and atmospheric pressure, and samples were extracted from the sheets of each group of polymer blends and hybrid composite materials according to ASTM D790 standard [12 and 13]. for each run, five samples were test and the average reading were taken.

3.2 Impact test

The impact test run out by instrument model XJU-22, supplied from Time group Inc., impact test is performed at room temperature according to (ISO-180) [14 and 15] by using Izod Impact test machine type is (XJU series pendulum Izod/Charpy impact testing machine). Samples of impact resistance were cut from the area along the (FSP) line and the results obtained are a mean of five readings per experiment.

4. Results and discussion

1. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometers (FTIR): Mid-infrared spectroscopy has been widely used for the characterization of organic compounds. Both qualitative and quantitative information can be obtained by this technique. So, vibrational spectroscopy has been considered an important tool in the elucidation of molecular structure; detailed analysis of IR for polymeric materials provides information on both intramolecular and as intermolecular interactions. The FTIR spectrum of the polymer blend (HDPE-15%PVC) is shown in Figure (4). With the base polymer blend absorption, the band observed at (2904.80 and 2852 cm^{-1}) confirms the presence of C-H₂ stretching band and CH₂ rocking and C-C stretching respectively [16 and 17]. The peak at 721.38 cm^{-1} referred to CH rocking mode, peaks at ($670.$ and 597 cm^{-1}) correspond to C-Cl stretching vibration mode [17 and 18]. Figures (5) show the IR spectrum of polymeric hybrid composite (HDPE: 15% PVC: Graphite, Al₂O₃, and Cu particles), which cannot observe significant differences between IR spectrums, except the intensity, for all characteristic peak of polymer blend composites, it's lower than polymer blend (85%HDPE: 15% PVC).

Figure 4. FTIR analysis of polymer blend (HDPE: 15% PVC).

Figure 5. FTIR analysis of polymer blend hybrid composites (HDPE 15%PVC: (6% Graphite, 6% Al₂O₃ and 6% Cu particles).

2. Flexural behavior: Figures (6-8) shows main effect plots on flexural strength, flexural modulus and Maximum shear stress of each variable of added particles (C: Al₂O₃; Cu) to the matrix material (HDPE: 15%PVC). As it is clear from these figures, that the outputs increase steadily with the increase in a percentage of particles content, in other words, when C particles ratio increased from the (2 to 6%) at a constant value of other parameters, flexural strength, flexural modulus and maximum shear stress increases by about 36% (22.14 MPa to 30.16 MPa), 128% (from 0.784 GPa to 1.79 GPa) and 48% (from 0.602 MPa to 0.892 MPa) respectively. As well as, it is evident from these figures, Al₂O₃ has little effect on outputs, for retaining the other factors constant, it was noticed as Al₂O₃ content increases from (2 to 6%) the flexural strength it has increased by 13% (25.5 MPa to 28.696 MPa), flexural modulus it has decreased by 0.58% (from 1.038 GPa to 1.032 GPa) and maximum shear stress it has increased by 16% (from 0.706 MPa to 0.816 MPa). Whereas, the effect of copper addition, there is a slight increase in the outputs. Based on the above results, the rate of increase in flexural strength, flexural modulus and maximum shear stress values of prepared composite samples depends on the filler types, their concentration ratio in the mixture and degree of compatibility between these particles [19].

Figure 6. Flexural strength of a polymeric blend composites, as a function of particles content (C, Al₂O₃, and Cu) in composites.

Figure 7. Flexural modulus of a polymeric blend composites, as a function of particles content (C, Al₂O₃, and Cu) in composites.

Figure 8. Max. shear stress of a polymeric blends composites, as a function of particles content (C, Al₂O₃, and Cu) in composites.

Figures (9-11) clearly show the effect of the (FSP) method regarding raising the values of Flexural strength, flexural modulus and Maximum shear stress in the formation of hybrid composite materials. Where the percentage of the increase is up to (38%), (43%) and (48%) from the values of flexural strength, flexural modulus and Maximum shear stress of the HDPE and the binary polymer blend (85%HDPE:15%PVC).

Figure 9. Flexural strength values of neat HDPE, binary polymer blend (85%HDPE: 15%PVC) and polymeric hybrid composite ((85%HDPE: 15%PVC): (6%C+6%Al₂O₃ + 6%Cu)).

Figure 10. Flexural modulus values of neat HDPE, binary polymer blend (85%HDPE: 15%PVC) and polymeric hybrid composite ((85%HDPE: 15%PVC): (6%C+6%Al₂O₃ + 6%Cu)).

Figure 11. Max. shear stress values of neat HDPE, binary polymer blend (85%HDPE: 15%PVC) and polymeric hybrid composite ((85%HDPE: 15%PVC): (6%C+6%Al₂O₃ + 6%Cu)).

3. Impact Strength: Figures (12, 13) show the main effect plot for impact strength and fracture toughness with the addition (C: Al₂O₃: Cu) particles to the matrix. It was noted from Figures (12,13) that the addition of particles of (graphite and alumina) to polymeric blend as matrix material, led to decreases the output values for both types of particles additives. It is evident that when the graphite and alumina percentage increased from (2 to 6%) in the blends, the impact strength and fracture toughness decreases. On the contrary, the effect of addition copper particles displays a reverse tendency. when increasing the percentage of added copper particles from (2 to 6%) increases the output values by ratios of (13 and 11%), respectively keeping the other parameters unchanged, this result is due to the high interfacial shear strength between copper particles and constituents of polymeric blends, and as a result of formation strong links and a good compatibility between components of composites materials, and this in turn lead to increase the energy required to failure [20and 21]. As well as, this is related to the participation of copper particles in increasing the energy needed to break the sample, which depends on the strength of the bonding of interface between the surface of the reinforcing materials(copper particles) and the constituents of a polymeric blend material.

Figure 12. Impact strength of polymeric blend composites, as a function of particles content (C, Al₂O₃, and Cu) in composites.

Figure 13. Fracture toughness of polymeric blend composites, as a function of particles content (C, Al₂O₃, and Cu) in composites.

Figures (14, 15) show the comparison of the impact strength and fracture toughness value between the HDPE, binary polymer blend and hybrid composite samples where the figures show the decrease in the values of outputs.

Figure 14. Impact strength values of neat HDPE, binary polymer blend (85%HDPE: 15%PVC) and polymeric hybrid composite ((85%HDPE: 15%PVC): (6%C+6%Al₂O₃ + 6%Cu)).

Figure 15. Fracture toughness values of neat HDPE, binary polymer blend (85%HDPE: 15%PVC) and polymeric hybrid composite ((85%HDPE: 15%PVC): (6%C+6%Al₂O₃ + 6%Cu)).

5. Morphology test

The properties of the polymer blend and its composites materials strongly depend on their morphology. Morphological information of fracture surfaces of binary polymeric blends and its composite, was studied using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The photographic imaging for fracture surface morphology of polymeric blend (85%HDPE:15%PVC), and its composites ((85%HDPE:15%PVC): (6%C+6%Al₂O₃ + 6%Cu) at magnification 2000X, was shown in Figure 16 (a and b) respectively, it was observed from the fracture surfaces of binary polymeric blend (figure 16 a) it was appeared as heterogeneous blends morphology, where appearance some of microstructures particles which was developed from the base material, and this may be related to the strong dipole moments, which is caused by the chlorine atoms. The large negative chlorine atoms, it will cause some steric hindrance and electrostatic repulsion, which reduces the flexibility of the polymer chains. This molecular immobility results in difficulty in the formation of the homogeneous polymer [22]. Further, fracture surface morphology of composites sample, it was observed through microscopic imaging (Figure (16 b), that the morphology of the fracture surface of the polymer composites showed sort of thing a homogeneous structure as compared with polymer blend morphology. where a homogeneous co-continuous structural morphology has appeared. Also, it does not observe any new phase emergence or phase separated dominants. As well as, it was observed from this morphology that, the most of the micro particles are embedded inside the matrix material, which acts as an integral part of the polymer blend structure. indicating to better interfacial adhesion between constituents of composite material. And this indicated to a good compatibility between the constituents of polymer blend and the reinforcement particles, which enhances the mechanical properties [23].

Figure 16. SEM for fracture surface morphology of polymer blends and its composites samples where: (a) for (85%HDPE:15%PVC) and (b) for ((85%HDPE:15%PVC): (6%C: 6%Al₂O₃: 6%Cu)). at (2000X) magnification

6. Conclusions

The friction stir processing (FSP) was strongly developed surface hybrid polymeric composite by choosing the proper conditions which were including: (rotational speed of (492 rpm), transversal speed (24 mm/min) using proper tool called shoe tool with proper pin geometry, plunging depth (0.5 mm) and dwell time 30 second). To obtain the effective hybrid polymeric composite, through the values of mechanical tests (flexural and impact strength), the highest increase in flexural strength, flexural modulus and Maximum shear stress was obtained with the addition of (6% graphite, 6% Al_2O_3 and 6% Cu) to the matrix (85%HDPE:15%PVC), where, the increase rate was reached to (38, 43 and 48%) respectively as compared to the matrix material, on the contrary the highest decrease in impact strength and fracture toughness was obtained with the addition of (2% graphite, 2% Al_2O_3 and 6% Cu) to the matrix, where, the decrease rate was reached to (6 and 20%) as compared to the matrix material. As well as, the results of prepared samples by FSP technique, it was confirmed by Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometers (FTIR) test and (SEM) test. According to the yields achieved, this confirms the success of the FSP technique to the development of different surface hybrid polymeric composite materials and most of these materials have high performance and without owning any internal or external flaws.

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